

Deliverable D6.3

Report on requirements for data quality and distributed analysis, as well as external resource interoperability

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1. Executive Summary

Description in the Grant Agreement:

Recommendations for data quality, resource interoperability (including EHDS and RIs), and ELSI based on use cases from Pillar III and recommendations from Pillar I, including requirements for distributed analysis

This deliverable describes the progress towards the understanding of data needs in the 1+MG infrastructure that are born from the fact that we are not building a data lake: not all data that needs to be analysed will be in the infrastructure, and the data that is in the infrastructure will not be all in the same place. The architecture of the infrastructure will make this as transparent as possible to the users of the data, but can't completely make the distributed nature invisible.

For the data that is in different places, agreements must be made about what data is included and how it is presented.

To be able to co-analyse data that is external to the 1+MG infrastructure, agreements must be in place about the interfaces and practical setup that is used to link the internal to the external data. This linkage is going to take place within each country and therefore is subject to the ethical and legal landscape in each country separately.

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

[Select 'Yes' (at least one) if the deliverable contributed to the key result, otherwise select 'No'. For more details of project outcomes, see [here](#)]

	Contributed
<p>Outcome 1</p> <p>Secure federated infrastructure and data governance needed to enable sustainable and secure cross border linkage of genomic data sets in compliance with the relevant and agreed legal, ethical, quality and interoperability requirements and standards based on the progress achieved by the 1+MG initiative.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 2</p> <p>Platform performing distributed analysis of genetic/genomic data and any linked clinical/phenotypic information; it should be based on the principle of federated access to data sources, include a federated/multi party authorisation and authentication system, and enable application of appropriate secure multi-party and/or high-end computing, AI and simulation techniques and resources.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 3</p> <p>Clear description of the roles and responsibilities related to personal data and privacy protection, for humans and computers, applicable during project lifetime and after its finalisation.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 4</p> <p>Business model including an uptake strategy explaining the motivation, patient incentives and conditions for all stakeholders at the different levels</p>	No

<p>(national, European, global) to support the GDI towards its sustainability, including data controllers, patients, citizens, data users, service providers (e.g., IT and biotech companies), healthcare systems and public authorities at large.</p>	
<p>Outcome 5</p> <p>Sustained coordination mechanism for the GDI and for the GoE multi-country project launched in the context of the 1+MG initiative.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 6</p> <p>Communication strategy – to be designed and implemented at the European and national levels.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 7</p> <p>Capacity building measures necessary to ensure the establishment, sustainable operation, and successful uptake of the infrastructure.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Outcome 8</p> <p>Financial support to the relevant stakeholders to enable extension, upgrade, creation and/or physical connection of further data sources beyond the project consortium or to implement the communication strategy and for capacity-building.</p>	<p>No</p>

3. Methods

This deliverable describes requirements for data quality and distributed analysis, as well as external resource interoperability, in the context of project task 6.3, "Investigating and recommending solutions to linking data between GDI and EHDS, for example PPRL. Submission support for GoE and other data sources."¹

These amount to the requirements that should be imposed on the data in the 1+MG infrastructure that is being built by GDI, in order for the infrastructure to be able to do its intended work of making the data available for different research projects, health care applications, quality control and statistics.. Because we want the data in the infrastructure to be available for varied goals that may be significantly different from the purpose for which they were originally collected, we can't simply rely on the individual data having been generated well enough to serve the reuse.

The architecture of GDI is centred around **datasets**, which are listed in a **catalogue**. A dataset is a collection of information that belongs together and is subject to the same governance. In the context of 1+MG, each dataset contains a set of comparable genetic and associated data from a group of somehow comparable data subjects. Within a dataset, mostly the same data fields are available for the described data subjects.

Each dataset needs metadata: the metadata of the dataset. This metadata comes in different types. In the context of the 1+MG infrastructure and its data catalogue, the dataset-level metadata is used by data re-users to identify potentially interesting datasets. The metadata includes bibliographic metadata: information like title, authors and description, such as defined in e.g. the Dublin Core². It contains provenance metadata: information about the source of the dataset and how it was obtained (e.g. "collected in the context of a clinical trial"). It also contains content description metadata: kind of data that is in the data set (e.g. "it contains whole genome sequencing data as well as medication history of the data subjects") and population description metadata about the subjects themselves (e.g. "data subjects are from the centre region of The Netherlands, between 18 and 65 years old, and half of them were diagnosed with diabetes mellitus type 1"). From this last example, it is obvious that the population description consists of *aggregated phenotypical information*. Another type of dataset-level metadata is ELSI (Ethical, Legal, Societal Issues) metadata. This describes the goals for which the data can be used (e.g. through consent) and is included so that a user can get a filtered view of datasets from the catalogue. All metadata will, in accordance with the FAIR principles, need to be made readable by machines as well as human beings.

Types of requirements that can be relevant for data and metadata in the 1+MG infrastructure are:

¹ The title of the task contains a number of abbreviations: Next to GDI for Genomic Data Infrastructure these are EHDS for European Health Data Space, PPRL for Privacy Preserving Record Linkage and GoE for Genome of Europe,

² <https://www.dublincore.org/specifications/>

- Data requirements, describing what is needed from the data to be able to use them in the infrastructure in coherence with data that is coming from elsewhere.
- Legal requirements, such as those imposed by the requirements of the GDPR (General Data Protection Regulation) and the expected role of the infrastructure in the EHDS (European Health Data Space) regulation. These are described by recommendations for the data governance from Pillar I.
- Practical/technical requirements, such as imposed by the federated nature of the data infrastructure.

The requirements described in this deliverable consider:

- Descriptive metadata generically needed for the infrastructure and its users.
- The possibility to associate (link) the data in the infrastructure to additionally available data on the same data subjects elsewhere. This builds on the sharing and linking guidelines from the B1MG project³.

Out of scope for this work are:

- The quality of the sample and methods that have been used to collect the data and process it. Description of some of these aspects has been done as part of the existing 1+MG framework in B1MG⁴ and the working groups of 1+MG initiative. The QUANTUM project⁵ will be defining a data quality label for the EHDS.
- The definition of metadata and description specifically required to identify suitable data through searches of the infrastructure. This is done by GDI WP4.
- Recommendations on data and metadata fields that are required for answering the questions from specific use cases. This is done by Task 8.2 in GDI WP8.
- Development and certification of Secure Multi-Party Computing techniques necessary to combine data about the same subjects across different secure processing environments. This is not yet a task in any current project known to us.

Three important contributions towards gathering the information presented in this deliverable have been the creation of a document titled "data inclusion scenarios" (currently in the process of being evaluated by the GDI governance panel), the organisation and running of a workshop on data linkage (2024-06-06, accomplishing GDI milestone 23) including preparation with two brainstorm sessions

³ Pinto, C., Belien, J., Ligtvoet, M., Urbini, M., Volkert, P., Gu, W., Tebaldi, M., Patocs, A., van der Velde, K. J., Swertz, M., van Gijn, Marielle, E., Korbel, J. O., Padella, A., Valencia, A., Muñoz, A., Pedrera, M., Serrano, P., Parra, C., Beltran, S., ... Haddad, T. (2022). B1MG D3.8 Documented best practices in sharing and linking phenotypic and genetic data –2v0. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7342855>

⁴ <https://framework.onemilliongenomes.eu/data-quality-inclusion>

⁵ <https://quantumproject.eu/>

earlier in the project, and a cross pillar I/II workshop about the technical consequences of the proposed data governance for the infrastructure (which took place 2024-09-13).

4. Description of work accomplished

The GDI project works on the realisation of a technical infrastructure for genomic data that will help instantiate the 1+MG initiative's ambitions. Two aspects of the structure of the data in the infrastructure are relevant for the considerations in this deliverable:

1. The 1+MG infrastructure is a **federated** infrastructure where algorithms are *by default* brought to the data for analysis rather than data being moved to a place where it will be analysed.
2. Research questions will often also require other data (on the same data subjects) that is not directly available in the 1+MG infrastructure, but only **linked** to it at the time of data release.

The data *federation* will require questions that need data from different member countries to be run in multiple different locations. In the world of federated analysis, this problem is referred to as horizontal partitioning. Facilitation of data that is horizontally partitioned requires that the data is presented as much as possible in the same way in all locations, and that the compute facilities available for the analysis in the different locations can be used with minimal adaptations to the analysis software. These issues will be addressed in section 4.1 below. In the 1+MG infrastructure, data will only be brought together in one place under unavoidable circumstances (as of yet not defined) and only when all data providers agree.

Data *linking* facilitates the use of genetic data from the 1+MG infrastructure in concert with other data about the same person. An often mentioned example is phenotypic data, but research projects can require many other types of data, like other molecular data (transcriptomics, proteomics, metabolomics), biological imaging data (radiology, pathology), and external data (socio-economic data, exposomics). In the world of federated analysis, this problem is referred to as vertical partitioning. Facilitation of data that is vertically partitioned requires access to record linking technology. This will be addressed in section 4.2 below.

Additional considerations required when dealing with data federation in combination with data linking will be described in section 4.3.

4.1 Recommendations for data quality and homogeneity for distributed analysis

The 1+MG infrastructure is envisioned to be a distributed infrastructure. Not only will the data that is included in the infrastructure be stored and kept close to where it has been collected, but where possible also analysis will be taking place where the data happens to be, rather than bringing the data closer to the data user. Federated analysis algorithms have not been developed for all

applications of genetics data; the 1+MG federated nature by default of the 1+MG infrastructure will require reusers to consider developing such federated algorithms. The incentive to develop and improve such algorithms will become much stronger once the 1+MG infrastructure is operational. Nevertheless, exceptional types of questions may still require analysis on all data in a central place or hybrid distributed/centralised; the conditions that will be used to judge whether a request for such exceptions will be honoured have not yet been established. Bringing the data together will bring ethical/legal as well as technical challenges, and 1+MG member countries may exclude this option for their data.

In the analysis below, the recommendations for the data have been split into two parts: a generic consideration of data sanity and data quality for the 1+MG infrastructure that is valid regardless of centralised or federated usage (4.1.1); and a subsection on additional considerations for federated access (4.1.2).

4.1.1 Data Sanity and Data Quality

DNA sequencing encompasses a diverse array of technologies, resulting in varying types and qualities of data. For instance, when examining human samples, we can opt for sequencing the entire genome (WGS) or just the exomes (WES), each yielding distinct datasets. Additionally, the quality of sequencing results can vary based on factors such as the starting material's quality, researcher-defined technical parameters (with associated costs), the equipment utilised, and potential errors during the process. Ideally, 1+MG would consist of a 100% homogeneous set of data: from D2.1 section 5.4 on Data Inclusion⁶: "The 1+MG dataset must ideally be as uniform as possible, including having minimal metadata standards attached to them, in order to be scientifically valuable." To achieve such a homogenous set of data, it is implied that only the data which comply with the set parameters are included, while excluding those which don't. Excluding data is nonetheless a potential threat to the success of a broad data collection, especially within a determined time-frame, and it brings with it the risk to exclude data which could be fit and valuable for some research purposes. In order to keep the infrastructure state of the art, the possible inclusion criteria will need to be reviewed to take into account technological advances.

Human sequencing data can be classified according to three groups of parameters:

- **Sequencing type.** Different kinds of results are obtained with different technologies and different starting materials. Those can be useful to answer diverse scientific questions.
- **Sanity level.** Sequencing data and metadata can include different defects and errors like incomplete mapping, file duplication within the same dataset, mismatching numbers of objects, mismatching data formats or mismatching coding within the correct format, corrupted files, mismatching biological values between sequencing files and their metadata.
- **Quality level.** Sequencing data and metadata can vary profoundly in quality, like the depth of sequencing coverage obtained, sample purity and sequencing accuracy. Metadata can be

⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10728049>

uniquely framed for certain use cases or complete enough to be suitable for a broad range of topics.

For each of these dimensions, it should be decided what level of heterogeneity in the infrastructure is allowed, both between infrastructure nodes and within each node participating in the infrastructure. For each allowed variation, suitable metadata handling should be developed describing these aspects for each dataset in the infrastructure. If, for example, the infrastructure allows both WES and WGS data, a potential user should be able to make this distinction through the search interface that is provided.

The GDI project itself is not in a position to make decisions on these points. Therefore, this question has been added to the “data inclusion scenarios” document that will allow the members of the 1+MG special group and national mirror groups to give their input on the implementation, based on a preliminary analysis of the different options that was provided. The recommendation coming out of that analysis is to accept a limited set of data types, set an absolute minimum threshold for data sanity, and accept variations in data quality without specifying minimum requirements but requiring thorough documentation of the achieved quality parameters. The Genome of Europe project will enforce quality standards like this: a sample must cover >80-90% of the hg38 genome 20 times. The average coverage must be 30x or higher. The mean and median coverage must be ± 1 . The contamination fraction must be <2%. It is obvious that the 1+MG infrastructure should never construct inclusion criteria that are incompatible with these.

4.1.2 Additional requirements identified for federated analysis

Federated data analysis is often discussed for the analysis of personal data, but existing federated analysis systems are usually created to answer a single question repeatedly, on data that evolves over time at the different participating sites⁷. A federated infrastructure as intended in GDI, where the data will be made available in a standard form to answer many different questions which are each usually run a single time, will be able to learn from this earlier experience with federated analysis (e.g. through the use of federated analysis frameworks, which encapsulate the experience; these are explored in Task 8.1) but **additional experience will have to be made in GDI itself** (again referring to Task 8.1).

For a federated analysis, algorithms are programmatically moved to the data where the analysis happens, and the user in principle has no direct access to data. Permissions may not cover tinkering or visualisation. The spectrum of options for federated analysis have been drawn in D8.4 *Report on federated data access scenarios*⁸. If no tinkering permissions have been given to the user, it is essential that the data looks the way the user can reasonably expect it to look, and the infrastructure behaves the way the user can reasonably be expecting it to behave. This is a **strong requirement for data homogeneity**. In addition it is essential that **proper procedures are defined for updating data sets** over time, so that users are not confronted with unexpected changes.

⁷ E.g. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.radonc.2019.11.019>

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8208439>

Maximisation of the data homogeneity includes the standardisation of the data acquisition and the analysis pipelines used to process the raw acquired sequencing data.

The 1+MG federated genomic "database" involves many different organisations, which means different operating practices such as inclusion of samples from multiple sequencing centres, sample preparation performed using different protocols, and analysed using different bioinformatics pipelines. All these practices can introduce batch effects. Bioinformatic pipelines are designed to identify variants that differ from the human reference genome and the required steps include base calling, read alignment, variant calling, and variant annotation. It is known that different pipelines have different accuracies and performances and harmonising these pipelines can mitigate batch effects.

Different use cases might want/need to use different bioinformatics pipelines: e.g. long read sequencing requires a pipeline different from short read sequencing. Also, somatic variant calling is different from germline variant detection. It is important that the use cases foreseen by the project help determine what are the best practices for the analysis pipeline and what is expected in terms of analysis, since this information can help shape the development and the cost of the infrastructure and help determine if it would be beneficial to reprocess the data ingested to the infrastructure according to specific pipelines prior to or after its transfer to the infrastructure. Any such reprocessing requirements can have serious implications for the organisation of the 1+MG nodes and the capacity provided by their data providers.

The estimated cost of processing a 30x short-read sequencing WGS for germline analysis is approximately €4.80 per genome using GATK v4 pipeline at a commercial cloud provider. The estimated cost of processing a WGS using long-read sequencing technology (Nanopore) using a commercial cloud is approximately €530,00⁹. Reprocessing a WGS dataset to harmonise the analysis pipeline therefore creates a financial burden proportional to the number of samples included in the infrastructure and the type of analysis performed. This cost can 1) be left to the data provider if the 1+MG establishes a standard for data analysis prior to deposition, or 2) be a cost to the infrastructure itself if there is a standard but the data providers are not obliged to follow it prior to data deposition, or 3) it can be a cost to a data reuser if the infrastructure decides to include non-harmonized data.

Bioinformatics pipelines are updated over time following new developments. Also, the reference genome used to map the sequencing data is subject to updates. Updates will pose a financial burden on the 1+MG infrastructure, if all data needs to be reprocessed. Also, **there is a need for a technical committee to make the decision of if/when to update the datasets**, and whether to keep the old data to facilitate reproducibility.

Algorithms for the alignment of short read sequencing and detection of single nucleotide variants/small indels are well-developed and benchmarked. However, that is not always the case for other types of sequencing and for structural variants. Use cases that require analysis of data for which there is no convergence in the analysis pipeline yet would probably prefer to re-analyze the

⁹ See <https://doi.org/10.1056/NEJMc2112090> table S17.

datasets using their own pipelines and it would be valuable to have this need assessed by the WP7 experts. It has to be determined what is the percentage of use cases that demand such type of analysis and what the computing resources needed would cost.

Another variable in the analysis pipeline is the reference genome used. If all data is deposited using the same pipeline (and reference genome), it makes a more homogeneous data offer. However, if data is aligned to different versions of the human genome reference, reusers of data would have to lift over the data or realign it, incurring more computational usage at the reuse moment (or at the data deposition stage, depending on the chosen approach). It is important to also consider that use cases might have such different pipelines that processing all data according to those requirements might imply having multiple copies of data, but processed differently.

For the variant frequency lookup use case, data should have the same reference genome (or be lifted over on the fly). If this use case also requires quality control of the dataset/variant location, all nodes should use the same parameters to specify these quality reports. This also highlights the important cross talk between use cases, legal requirements and technical implementation.

It is noteworthy that the 1+MG infrastructure will also contain phenotypic data and might contain clinical data. Although there are pipelines specific to processing those data, the scope of this analysis will remain on the genomic data and the challenges imposed by it.

Besides using the same pipeline to decrease the severity of batch effects, data ingested to the infrastructure can be checked for errors and mismatches such as the ones in section 4.1.1. This sanity check of the files can be made upon data deposition and some options are discussed with more depth in the data quality check. Although sanity checks can be done in individual datasets to detect duplicate individuals during deposition, the federated nature of the infrastructure makes it difficult to detect duplicate individuals in different nodes (i.e., an individual is sequenced in projects or healthcare settings located in different countries). It would be important to orient data reusers to perform checks for duplicated data when analysing the ensemble of data made available to them from different data providers..

Additional complexity in achieving homogeneity is expected if the data user is bringing in their own genomic data, e.g. by adding an extra node to the analysis federation. To overcome this complexity, **the users will need access to the complete documentation describing the data inclusion**, so that they can make sure that their self-added data is treated the same way.

4.2 Recommendations for external resource interoperability including ELSI

Many potential applications of the genomic data that will be captured in the 1+MG infrastructure require more than just the plain genetic information. Phenotypic and other contextual information may be required, which will keep evolving over the lifetime of the data subject.

Here, we attempt to capture considerations that apply to the connection between the genomic information and the contextual information. A large part of this information was collected in two brainstorm sessions that were organised in the GDI project during 2023.

Prototypical subject search queries

The 1+MG infrastructure will allow data re-users to operate on data that they have requested access to. In order to consider the kind of functionality that is needed to identify suitable data for reuse, we formulated some prototypical search queries that could identify suitable subjects that will help answer a research question. Roughly sorted in order of increasing complexity, these are:

- Subjects from a specific geographic region
- Subjects with a specific genotype. Example: "I am looking for WGS data for people with an insertion in the XYZ gene".
- Subjects with a specific phenotype. Example "I am looking for WGS data for people who lived to at least an age of 85" or "I am looking for WGS data for people over 65 for whom we know whether they have diabetes mellitus type 2"
- Subjects with a specific genotype / phenotype combination: Example: "I am looking for WGS data for patients with diabetes mellitus type 1 who have a variation in the XYZ gene"
- Subjects along any of the lines above, for which specific other information is or may be available elsewhere. Example: "I want WGS data for Alzheimer patients for which a brain MRI scan is also available."

The GDI project will start building the functionality for easier questions (the so-called Minimal Viable Product, MVP) and work towards more complex problems later. Even if the functionality for the more complex questions would not be built as part of the GDI project, the architecture of the infrastructure should permit that this functionality is added later.

Storyline: Searching data suitable for a particular case of re-use

The envisioned workflow for GDI is that a prospective re-user of data (especially a researcher):

1. Will use a catalogue to identify datasets that potentially could contain data of (a substantial number of) suitable data subjects.
2. Will use Beacon technology to obtain an indication of the actual number of data subjects in each identified data set.
3. Will make a single request for the data about all the matching data subjects from different data providers.
4. If access is granted, will make use of that data.

This process targets the minimisation of processing of personal information, for legal reasons as well as for reasons of scalability.

Step 1 can be considered successful if a researcher can use the catalogue to identify all datasets that contain suitable subjects, while at the same time excluding most datasets that do not contain any suitable subjects. It is important to realise that the only information the catalogue contains that

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can be used to realise this goal is the dataset-level metadata (see section above): descriptive metadata of each dataset that is anonymous through aggregation.

A strict selection of suitable datasets in this phase is necessary for data minimization as well as for scalability of the searching infrastructure. If no sufficient restriction is reached in this phase, extensive beacon queries will have to be performed. This is both costly, and harder to justify under the GDPR since processing of personal data should always be minimised.

Timing of Data Linking

Data linking in 1+MG is relevant at two different moments: when data is included into the infrastructure, and when data is made available for reuse.

Data linking at the time of data inclusion

Data linking at the time of data inclusion into the 1+MG infrastructure is necessary to enable data discovery by a reuser. As can be seen in the prototypical questions above, many practical questions require phenotypic information in order to be able to identify suitable data subjects for a research question.

Two processes are supported by the pre-inclusion linking:

- The creation of the aggregated dataset-level metadata
- The loading of phenotypic information into the 1+MG beacon(s)

Both of these processes can use linked data sources that are as fixed as the (genomic) dataset itself: If the dataset is fixed, the phenotypic information could get stale, but it may not require updating to serve the purpose of data discovery. If the dataset itself is regularly updated, the associated phenotypic information can also be kept up-to-date.

What type of other data sources need linking?

- Phenotypes required to fill the (minimal) phenotypic data models for the use cases as discussed in Task 8.2
- The existence of other data (e.g. transcriptomics, proteomics, metabolomics, or imaging radiology/pathology, or exposomics and socio-economics data) for the same subject. Note that such data content will never be available through 1+MG; what is needed is a **flag** that it is available, either at the subject level or at the dataset level, and a **pointer** (e.g. persistent identifier) so that it can actually be located when needed.

Data linking at the time of data release to a reuser

Four types of data linking have been identified to be relevant around the time of data release:

- **Relinking at release time to the data that was available when the genomic data was included in GDI.** This can be needed to ensure the availability of the latest clinical information of the data subjects for the re-user. If all that is needed by the reuser is the clinical data that is

included in the 1+MG infrastructure (approximately the data from the minimal phenotypical description as created by Task 8.2), no external linking will need to be performed, but a repeat of the clinical data extraction performed at the time of data inclusion may still be required to ensure the latest information is made available.

- **Linking to another resource that is requested by the re-user and that is available to the data release committee¹⁰.** This can be done at the time when data minimization takes place, and the resulting data can be released in the same Secure Processing Environment at the same time to the user and appear as a single dataset.
- **Linking to another resource that is requested by the re-user and that can only be made available in its own secure processing environment.** Computing on the ensemble of information may require the development of Secure Multi Part Computing (SMPC) algorithms approved by the Data Access Committee of at least one of the data resources, since it must be possible to ascertain that no personal data is leaving one SPE in order for the data combination to be brought about. The development and certification of SMPC methods is outside of the scope of the GDI project.
- **Linking to resources that are already under the control of the re-user.** This would require that the user is allowed to bring his own data into the SPE, and that the data that is released to the user includes the necessary linking keys.

Note that data variables from outside of GDI do not come with GDI quality and consistency assurance. For data that will be combined in the context of the EHDS, the recently started QUANTUM project will be developing quality assurance standards.

Linking between data from GDI and other data that is available in the EHDS will likely become a very frequent need. Future work should evaluate whether EHDS and GDI can share parts of the infrastructure to avoid the need of SMPC for such questions. Similarly data linking from 1+MG with data from other EHDS Authorised Participants, such as an EDIC that is under construction in the EUCAIM project can be important, e.g. for cancer use cases correlating imaging and genetic information. Research could benefit if governance allows analysis of such data linked into a single SPE environment. Modularising the security features of the SPE setup could be a very important aspect to explore, to avoid that all processing always will be required to be performed in the strictest possible highest level security environment.

Linking Keys

Linking datasets together, merging information about the same data subject into a single data record, needs to be done based on linking keys: basically pieces of identifying information that are present in all of the resources that need to be linked. From the brainstorming session it was concluded that this is done differently in every country; description of such processes in a standard

¹⁰ *Data release committee* is an *ad hoc* term here for the group of people that can combine resources to be released to the data reuser; e.g. in Finland this is done by the data access committee. In many other countries this has not yet been decided. We nevertheless want to make the distinction here because combining data sets is not the same type of task as taking a decision over an access request.

operating procedure (SOP) may not be required in GDI. Internationally linking data about the same data subject would be very hard because of the differences between countries, and in the discussions we found little benefit of doing so. It was therefore decided that international linking would not be pursued. A small risk of data subject duplication between different countries exists. That risk can even not be completely excluded between datasets within one country.

In the 2024-06-06 workshop on data linking, Dieter Hayn from the Austrian Institute of Technology has given an overview¹¹ of data linking techniques. His presentation focused on the selection of techniques that can be used to link records without disclosing information about the data subjects to other entities: neither between the partners who hold the data sets that should be linked, nor between those partners and a trusted third party that is used to facilitate the linkage. Dieter's presentation also pointed out several other features of linking technologies that can be important for selection. Altogether, the features were:

- Techniques that function directly between data holders vs techniques that require a trusted third party, a pseudonymisation service.
- The subject identification information, together defining the linking key, can be directly shared or can be shared between parties in encrypted form. Only in encrypted form a technique is really privacy preserving: in that case for the matching process nobody can see any identifying information that is not already under their control.
- A pseudonymisation service based on exchange of encrypted versions of the identifying information will not be able to identify matches between records in case of typo's or incomplete matches, unless specific provision for this is taken in the algorithms.
- After pseudonymisation, data records can be exchanged between parties; alternatively the data themselves can be encrypted and calculations themselves can be privacy preserving (keywords: secure multi party computing; homomorphic encryption).

Dieter explained also that the different complexity of some of the systems makes them more or less suitable for larger or smaller consortia, and to be maintained for a longer time. Only very advanced systems will be able to match records even when the identifying information used for matching is changing over time, e.g. to adapt to changes in the laws applicable to data linking.

Dieter also pointed out two different pseudonymisation services that are operating in a European context: SPIDER¹² and EUPID¹³; both services are privacy preserving (third parties who do not know the identifying information), with a functional difference: EUPID (which is the service provided by Dieter's own organisation) also facilitates the exchange and linking of previously pseudonymized data, where SPIDER only facilitates record matching between data holders who each are in possession of the identifying information.

¹¹ The presentation slides are available for project members in the project environment under <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1wulk78j7wEdnGuwxh1Z7MJy01kfGiJJp/view?usp=sharing>

¹² <https://eu-rd-platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/spider/>

¹³ <https://services.eupid.eu/>

As described, the linking of data for the 1+MG infrastructure is only performed within each national node and never between nodes, and what variables can be used as linking keys is dependent on national legislation. It is therefore left to each of the national implementations to choose a suitable linking technology.

4.3 Considerations for federated analysis in combination with linking data

There are a few considerations to be made when 1+MG data is combined with other data through data linkage in different countries, and used for federated analysis. Differences in linking techniques in different locations could lead to:

- Differences in completeness of linking if the linked data is not brought to the same standards like the genetic data in GDI
- Differences in the quality of linking (e.g. if some countries can do deterministic linking, and others have to rely on empirical methods).
- Aspects that a trained (AI) qualifier could recognize as differences, but which are irrelevant for the question at hand. Such aspects need to be compensated for in federated learning applications.

Additional complexity may occur when data stays vertically partitioned: if data that is linked together for the research can not be brought into the same SPE, but needs to be analysed between different SPEs using Secure Multi Party Computing (SMPC): the vertical partitioning in this case could be different in different countries, not only because the linking keys may differ, but also because the data is being maintained by different data providers (e.g. in one country the first provider has columns A, B, C made available in one SPE, and a second provider has columns D and E made available in another SPE, and in another country A and B are maintained by one party whereas C, D and E come from another data provider and the split over the two SPEs is different). As a consequence, SMPC configuration or even SMPC algorithms may need to be redeveloped for each country separately.

5. Results

- An infrastructure that relies on federated analysis requires homogeneity in the data provided to re-users; homogeneity was also foreseen as a goal in itself, and we have been able to identify what needs to be done to establish it.
- Two brainstorming sessions on data linkage held in 2023 identified data linkage issues and reached first decisions on the path to be followed by the infrastructure.
- Workshop on data linkage (with 38 attendees) provoking discussion and informing a larger group on privacy preserving record linkage techniques and interactions with EHDS
- Process created to pose questions from the project to the governance panel.

1+MG has set the target that re-users of data should be facilitated as much as possible. This includes the need to provide comparable data even if they are coming from different sources: data homogeneity. Our analysis shows that this homogeneity is very important also because of the

federated nature of the 1+MG infrastructure. To achieve homogeneity, the infrastructure should establish data inclusion criteria that select desired data types, check the sanity of the data, and document data quality. In addition the 1+MG infrastructure needs to define "gold standard" pipelines and choose a reference genome, and make pre-processed data available to re-users that use these gold standards.

The two brainstorm sessions that kickstarted the work on linking data described in this deliverable picked the brains of many people with expertise in different aspects of data linkage. As an important result of that, a large group of people in the project was made aware of the entire spectrum of issues to be solved. In working out the results we have come to a number of example scenarios and prototypical questions, which could be explored. The workshop on data linkage that was held 2024-06-06 brought these conclusions to representatives from many nodes in the project, and was also used to bring in information about the setup of the EHDS and consequences for the 1+MG infrastructure. We also learned about privacy preserving record linkage. Each country participating in the infrastructure will need to implement the presented techniques separately, based on available linking keys and the local legal landscape describing their use.

We identified that there are two distinct moments data need to be linked: at the time of data inclusion to facilitate the discoverability, and at the time of data release to facilitate a large fraction of the uses of the infrastructure.

Many thoughts have gone into a document describing 5 questions raised in the technical pillar of the GDI project. These specific five questions will be discussed with the governance panel in a workshop on 2024-10-01, and two of the consideration sections from the document have been used in section 4 above since they so clearly express the issues of data quality and diversity.

6. Discussion

- The goal of the deliverable has been achieved. Next steps have been identified and are described in section 8.
- Fragmentation of data into different countries and governance structures makes it necessary to align.
- Technical solutions have been described that are needed to use data from different organisations.
- We call into consideration the option of avoiding or actively reducing data governance fragmentation where possible.

The possibility of data linkage is essential to the vast majority of possible uses of the data that will be collected in 1+MG. This document describes the difficulties that need to be solved, and shows that these difficulties, on data and/or governance level, can be very large in a fragmented data landscape. The landscape is fragmented through differences between countries, and through differences between 1+MG infrastructure and other related data infrastructures that are relevant for data linkage.

Next to presenting the technological requirements for the data and metadata that can be pursued to overcome data fragmentation (i.e. facilitate data linkage and federation), this deliverable is therefore also a plea to work on defragmenting the data landscape where possible. In a defragmented landscape, research and other purposes of the 1+MG collection will be much easier, and possibly therefore faster and less expensive to achieve.

7. Conclusions & Impact

- Data linking is mostly a responsibility that lies within the nodes.
- A communication structure with the 1+MG governance has been established to answer open questions.
- Prototype questions with different linking complexity have been created; these can be used to implement solutions successively in the infrastructure.
- We call for collaborations reducing complexity of governance for linked data sources.

The described work created clarity about the responsibilities for linking data: most of the burden will be with the member countries in the infrastructure. Data linkage was described as essential to realise the goals of the 1+MG infrastructure, and as a hard problem.

We developed a process to further specify development directions in the infrastructure through a formalised way of passing questions to the governance panel of the project about the direction to take in case the answers can not be taken under the responsibilities of the project itself. The first 5 questions have been passed on already and will be discussed soon.

We have identified a number of prototype questions that show a spectrum of complexity for data linkage. The infrastructure will start with the implementation of the most simple case, and will need to work, both during the GDI project and after, on support for successively more complex questions. The experience with the easier cases will be indispensable for the implementation of the more complex ones later.

We have seen from our analysis that consistency in data quality is essential for federated analysis and we have identified that this is hard when data sources are maintained under different governance. Also, differences in governance can lead to differences in requirements on data processing and security, and could lead to very complex situations with federations of vertically partitioned data. Genetics research very often will involve data that is not under the governance of the 1+MG infrastructure, and health research in the future will involve more and more genetics data. Therefore defragmentation of the data landscape will be very important.

8. Next steps

A good basis has been created for the understanding of the needs for data linkage. On a number of points, further work will be required. In identifying these, we did not stop at the end of the GDI projects: some of these can be undertaken as part of the planned work in the GDI project, other parts

in the infrastructure beyond the GDI project, and yet others in the 1+MG initiative in relation to other initiatives:

- Experts in WP7 of GDI should be asked to create an inventory of re-usable data pre-processing pipelines and the breadth of their use, so that a decision can be taken by 1+MG on which pre-processed data should become part of the infrastructure.
- Once the infrastructure is running simple use cases that do not require external linking, we should aim to try use cases that link to external data, in order of increasing complexity and functionality. This may be a task for the operational infrastructure after the GDI project has come to an end.
- Linking between data from GDI and other data that is available in the EHDS will likely become a very frequent need. Future work should evaluate whether EHDS and GDI can share parts of the infrastructure so that the need for the development of secure multi party computing solutions (SMPC) for such questions can be avoided. Where infrastructure components (not only technical but also governance structures) can be shared, data linking will become much easier.
- The current *Data Inclusion Scenarios* document described 5 initial questions. Next step for these is to discuss them with the members of the Governance panel. This will take place in a workshop planned for 2024-10-01. If further questions arise, a similar process can be followed.
- To our knowledge, there is no work being undertaken to develop SMPC solutions needed when governance is different and vertical partitioning unavoidable. We should closely monitor upcoming needs and make sure such development processes are started in time.
- It is essential that the features for Secure Processing Environments are ironed out. Work on this may be performed in the TEHDAS2 and EOSC ENTRUST projects which should be followed by the GDI project and the 1+MG initiative. Features for SPEs should be defined in a modular way so as to avoid that all computation needs to be done under the strictest safety conditions, since this will be unnecessarily expensive and cumbersome.
- The 1+MG initiative describes that under certain conditions data from different member countries can be brought together into a single SPE to avoid the need for federated analysis. No effort has commenced yet to define the conditions under which this would be permissible. Here also, linkage with data under different governance needs to be taken into account.
- Efforts to explore the setup for federated analysis are needed specifically to get experience with the setup of federated analysis systems suitable for answering multiple different questions, without extensive "tinkering" of the data.
- A description needs to be created of the processes that are needed to release data, *linked* from different sources and *minimised*, to the data reuser in the secure processing environment.

